

“Whose knowledge counts? Whose knowledge is available? Whose knowledge circulates widely?”

Who does and who doesn't have access to knowledge is something Gore cares deeply about. They think research should be easily and freely available. When publishing their book, “Between HIV Prevention and LGBTI Rights: The Political Economy of Queer Activism in Ghana”, they chose open access to ensure there weren't any geographical or financial barriers and that everyone who participated in the research could access it.

Academics, activists and institutions in the Global South often have limited access to research due to the cost of academic books and paywalls.

By publishing open access, Gore says anyone and everyone will have access, regardless of where they live.

Research that circulates widely also tends to have more impact. It is more likely to stimulate debate, challenge established narratives and influence policy, for example.

That is important to Gore: “I'm hoping it's not just academics and researchers that read it. I'd like to think it is of interest to policymakers, activists, civil society organisations in Africa and around the world who are concerned about LGBTI rights and the struggle for queer liberation.”

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Why Gore believes equity of access is important

Knowledge should be available to everyone who wants and needs it

People shouldn't be disadvantaged because of their location or economic position

Research can be circulated far and wide

Different voices and perspectives can surface

Some of the ongoing Global North - Global South power imbalances can be addressed